

Study of Different Thermal Spray Coating Materials against Erosion in Boiler applications

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ABSTRACT

Erosion is one of the major problems in many engineering systems, including power generation units, steam/jet turbines, chemical processing equipment, and aircraft engines. Slurry erosion of turbine components in hydropower plants is a serious problem faced all over the world. Researchers are continuously working on investigating ways to mitigate the effects of slurry erosion. Different techniques are employed to protect the material from the deterioration of its life. Technologies such as filtration of the sand particles were carried out to reduce the amount of sand particles in the water that is impacting the turbine components and design the shape of the turbine components in such a manner as to mitigate the effect of slurry erosion. Still, slurry erosion is the most prioritized area among the researchers as it is causing heavy economic losses.

Keywords: Erosion, Coating, HVOF, Thermal spray, Hardness.

1. Introduction

The materials used for high-temperature applications are subjected to high-temperature erosion and wear in an industrial environment. Chandler reported that the coal gas environment contains many undesirable species, including sulfur, sodium, vanadium, etc. At this high temperature, erosion develops with the molten salt fluxing the protective oxide scale or directly dissolving the metal. Also, the impact of fly ash and unburned carbon particles on the surface of heated boiler tubes causes erosion called fly ash erosion [1]. High-temperature oxidation and erosion of heat exchanger tubes and other structural materials in coal-fired boilers are recognized as being the main cause of downtime at power-generating plants, which could account for 50–75% of their total arrest time [2]. Bellman studied that maintenance costs for replacing broken tubes in some installations are also very high and can be estimated at up to 54% of the total production costs. The materials used in these installations are fabricated from low-alloy carbon steels with chromium and molybdenum as the primary alloy additions. Although chromium is expected to impart erosion resistance to high-temperature alloys through the formation of a passive oxide layer on the alloy surface, its concentration in boiler tube alloys is not sufficient to form a protective external scale [3]. Marques The present materials capable of resisting erosive environments are highly alloyed and thus expensive. In search of cost-effective solutions for erosion problems, various coatings, like thermally sprayed coatings, have become attractive. Seven graded steels under solid particle impacts at room temperature and elevated temperature and found that oxidation is more influential on the erosion condition. Coal-fired power plants are the traditional and major source of electric power generation in India [4]. Hutchings reported that the There are four major divisions in a coal-fired thermal power plant, which include a turbine, boiler, coal handling system, and electrical energy handling system. Among these divisions, the boiler is a crucial and critical part of a coal-fired power plant. The major components of the boiler are boiler walls, economizers, air heaters, and super-heater tubes. The fly ash particles entrained in the fluidized bed impact the surface of boiler tubes and are deposited on the boiler tube components, causing erosion wear. In the advanced stages of degradation of the component material, the service life of boilers and their parts gets shorter. This requires the shutting down of the power station unit to replace the damaged parts or components. Erosion wear of the engineering materials is affected by operating conditions including impact angle, particle velocity, and temperature; impacting particle properties such as size, shape, density, and hardness; and target

material properties such as hardness, roughness, strength, and toughness, etc. Among these parameters, impact angle and temperature play a vital role in the erosion process. There is no universal model to predict the effectiveness of these parameters [5]. Sundararajan reported that the experimental study of these parameters on the erosion process is one of the most effective ways to analyze the erosion mechanism. studied the erosion behavior of pipeline steel at particle speeds ranging from 20 to 80 m/s and impact angles of 30° and 90°. The authors have found that the plowing mechanism is dominant at a 90° impact angle while cutting at a 30° impact angle. Anton investigated the behavior of fat at elevated temperatures under the oblique angle of impact [6]. Meringolo studied the solid particle erosion behavior of SS304 at room temperature and found that the higher erosion occurs at 30° as compared to the 90° impact angle, which indicated a ductile mode of erosion mechanism. evaluated the erosion rate of AISI 1018 and AISI 1080 steel with varying particle velocity and impact angles and found that the erosion rate increases with increasing particle velocity and decreases with increasing impact angle [7]. Chandler studied the erosion behavior of the CY5SnBiM cast alloy at room temperature. The author found that impact angle is a more dominant parameter in comparison to impingement velocity while the erosion test is occurring. Wear scars are found to be elliptical, mostly at 30°, 60°, and 90°, and circular at 90°. evaluated the erosion characteristics of high-Cr cast iron at 1173 K and found that at high temperatures, more Cr content has better erosion resistance [8]. Trilok Singh studied the microstructural characteristics of the eroded surface of AISI 310 steel and found that most of the sections are affected by plastic deformation, plowing, cracking, and flaking as shown in figure 1 [9].

Figure 1: Representation of crack formation in single particle impact

2. Erosion

Erosion is the progressive loss of material from a solid surface as a result of mechanical interaction between the solid surface and a multi-component fluid or impacting solid particles or liquid. Erosion occurs when solid particles entering a fluid stream (gaseous or liquid) strike a surface. In actual service conditions, solid particle erosion is usually in the form of component thinning, macroscopic scooping following the gas or particle flow, surface roughening, a lack of the directional grooving characteristic of abrasion, and, in some cases, the formation of ripple patterns on metal surfaces. Solid particle erosion is an essential material degradation mechanism encountered in a number of engineering systems, such as thermal power plants, aircraft gas turbine engines, pneumatic bulk transport systems, coal gasification plants, and coal slurry pipe lines. The worst-case scenarios

normally occur where there is a combination of both erosion and oxidation, particularly in the cases of erosion and high-temperature oxidation. In industrial applications and power generation, solid particles are formed during the combustion of pulverized coal, heavy oils, and synthetic fuels. In order to mitigate the effect of the slurry erosion testing regime, Cathodic protection was provided. It was also proved that any damage to the surface could be attributed to pure erosion and, as such, be assessed against the dry erosion test data. To identify the mechanism of failure of the coatings, the researchers analyzed the SEM images of eroded surfaces and observed that impinging slurry results in wear scars over the surfaces. Results obtained after testing revealed variation in the level of degradation experienced by each type of coating under the respective test conditions. It was found that tungsten carbide gives the best result for both dry erosion and slurry erosion testing. Researchers also established the relationship between hardness and thickness.

It was observed that the hardness of the coating increased with the thickness of the coating up to some critical value, and it started to decrease with an increase in the thickness of the coating. There is a general perception that the hardness of a coating increases with an increase in thickness. very high and can be estimated at up to 54% of the total production costs. Coal is a complex fuel that contains a varying amount of sulfur and a substantial fraction of non-combustible mineral constituents, commonly called ash. The coal used in Indian power stations contains ash (about 50%), consisting of abrasive mineral species (hard quartz up to 15%), which cause erosion of tubes. During the combustion of coal, the mineral matter is transformed into fly ash, which is deposited on the heat transfer surfaces of boilers. The heat transfer tubes of the boilers used in thermal power plants are subjected to intolerable levels of surface degradation by the combined cause of erosion mechanisms, resulting in tube wall thinning and unfortunate failure. High-temperature surface erosion by the impact of fly ash and unburnt carbon particles is one of the main problems in coal-fired boilers. More than one-quarter of boiler tube causes as shown in table 1. In the case of a coal-fired boiler at a power plant in the north-western region of India, it is reported that out of 89 failures occurring in one year, 50 were found to be due to erosion.

2.1 Types of failures at elevated temperatures

The main objective of any power plant is to provide an uninterrupted power supply, and it slowly depends on the continuous functioning of its components. Improper functioning of any one component (boiler tubes, super-heater, and turbine) can lead to the shutdown of the whole power plant. Boiler tube failures are one of the most common problems reported in power plants. Boiler tubes are mainly made up of cast iron, stainless steel, and high-temperature alloys. In order to prevent boiler tube failures, a deep investigation needs to be done so that the exact cause of the failure may be known. However, in the literature, different classifications are available with regards to the principle failure mechanisms of thermal power plant components as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Boiler tube failure mechanisms

2.2 Protective coatings

Coatings provide a way of extending the limits of use of materials at the upper end of their performance capabilities by allowing the mechanical properties of the substrate materials to be maintained while protecting them against wear or hot erosion. The role of coating as a corrosion barrier is similar to the role of oxide layers. The coating is protective if it prevents the outward diffusion of metal cations and the inward diffusion of elements that could react with the substrate material. Oxide layers forming on metals in reactions with the atmosphere are self-healing to a certain extent. If the oxide layer wears off or breaks up, a new oxide layer with almost equivalent properties will form. Thermal spraying has emerged as an important tool of increasingly sophisticated surface engineering technology. Various properties of the coating, such as thermal or electrical insulation, can be achieved using different coating techniques and coating materials. The term thermal spray describes a family of processes that use chemical or electrical energy to melt and accelerate particles of a material, which are then deposited on a surface. The quality of the coatings obtained by thermal spray techniques is related to the nature of the process and the processing parameters. On the other hand, thermal spray coatings are a good option to repair components and prevent excessive wear because, during the deposition process, no significant changes to the microstructure of substrates or excessive deformation are promoted.

In recent years, thermally sprayed coatings have also been increasingly applied to boiler tubes, particularly in vulnerable areas, in an effort to reduce erosion rates and prolong tube life. Manish Roy studied the Generally, these coatings appear to be chosen on the basis of their good high-temperature oxidation resistance and are mainly alloys containing high quantities of nickel and/or chromium. While it has been reported that uniformly deposited and coherent metallic coatings can provide erosion protection, only a few systematic experiments have been undertaken to quantify the erosion performance of these materials [10].

TABLE 1: Failure mechanisms of boiler tubes and their causes.

SL. NO	Failure mechanisms	Causes
1	Stress rupture	Short term overheating. High temperature creep (including long term over heating)
2	Fatigue	Vibration fatigue Thermal fatigue Creep fatigue
3	Erosion	Ash deposit and erosion Fly ash Falling slag Fuel particles: coal, peat
4	Lack of quality control and monitoring	Maintenance cleaning damage Material defects Welding defects Loss of metal

3. Literature review

Huttunen-Saarivirta Studied by using a veiled plasma spray technique, coatings of NiCrAlY and Ni₃Al were applied to boiler tube steels in accordance with ASTM-SA210-Grade A1 ASTM standards. Before adding Ni₃Al coatings, a bond coat of NiCrAlY was also applied. The coatings were analyzed, and the literature survey emphasizes that significant effort has been made to control erosion in coal-fired boilers and to describe this form of alloy degradation. Progress has been made on both of these fronts. In most instances where limiting erosion problems are encountered in boiler tube alloys, it will not be possible to modify the composition of the alloys to effectively combat these problems and still retain the desired mechanical properties. Improved resistance coatings must be developed for essentially unmodified alloys. It is clear from the literature that the coatings presently used in power plant boilers are either resistant to erosion or It is important to formulate coatings that are resistant to combined erosion and degradation. Plasma-sprayed composites and conductive coatings containing carbides and oxides dispersed in the tough matrix are now being addressed to combat degradation in a wide range of situations where components must survive in aggressive, high-temperature, multicomponent gas environments. Also, in the case of NiCrAlY bond coatings, significant hardness loss was the behavior of the coatings as a result of their melting [11]. mechanisms to formulate and test new coatings but also to understand the behavior of coatings and their degradation mechanisms in the aggressive boiler environment as widely as possible using SEM/EDAX, XRD, and metallography. All through the cross-section, the coatings' microhardness has been measured. In the case of NiCrAlY bond coatings, significant hardness loss was observed following laser remelting [11].

Matthews reported that the Under isothermal circumstances at a temperature of 900°C, the oxidation behavior of T-91 steel and T-22 steel in salts of 75 weight percent Na₂SO₄ and 25 weight percent NaCl has been investigated in a cyclic way. At 900°C, oxidation kinetics for T-91 steel and T-22 steel in salt were developed. Using the thermogravimetric method for 50 cycles under cyclic

circumstances. Each cycle took two hours to complete: one hour of heating at 900°C and 20 minutes of cooling in the air. Both samples almost followed the oxidation-parabolic rate rule. The oxide scales were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy/energy dispersive X-ray (SEM/EDAX) methods. During salt oxidation, T-91 steel was shown to be more erosion-resistant than T-22 steel. The current study examines the erosion resistance of Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings applied to Superni 75, Superni 718, and Superfer 800 H superalloys using a detonation cannon (D-gun). These superalloy substrates' deposited coatings have a virtually homogeneous, adherent, and dense microstructure with a porosity of less than 0.8%. In order to evaluate the high temperature of uncoated and Cr₃C₂-NiCr-coated superalloys in a molten salt environment (Na₂SO₄-60% V₂O₅) for 100 cycles, the thermogravimetry technique is applied. By employing XRD, SEM, and FE-SEM/EDAX to introduce their microstructural and compositional characteristics, the erosion products of the detonation gun-sprayed Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings on superalloys are examined in order to clarify the erosion mechanisms. In the provided molten salt environment at 900 °C, it is demonstrated that Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings on Ni- and Fe-based superalloy substrates are particularly efficient in reducing the erosion rate. In particular, compared to Superni 75 and Superni 718, the coating applied to Superfer 800 H provided superior erosion resistance. using SEM/EDAX, XRD, and metallography. All through the cross-section, the coatings' microhardness has been measured. In the case of NiCrAlY bond coatings, significant hardness loss was observed following laser remelting [12].

Vasudev studied the Under isothermal circumstances at a temperature of 900°C, the oxidation behavior of T-91 steel and T-22 steel in salts of 75 weight percent Na₂SO₄ and 25 weight percent NaCl has been investigated in a cyclic way. At 900°C, oxidation kinetics for T-91 steel and T-22 steel in salt were developed. Using the thermogravimetric method for 50 cycles under cyclic circumstances. Each cycle took two hours to complete: one hour of heating at 900°C and 20 minutes of cooling in the air. Both samples almost followed the oxidation-parabolic rate rule. The oxide scales were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy/energy dispersive X-ray (SEM/EDAX) methods. During salt oxidation, T-91 steel was shown to be more erosion-resistant than T-22 steel. The current study examines the erosion resistance of Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings applied to Superni 75, Superni 718, and Superfer 800 H superalloys using a detonation cannon (D-gun). These superalloy substrates' deposited coatings have a virtually homogeneous, adherent, and dense microstructure with a porosity of less than 0.8% [13].

Kaur reported that in order to evaluate the high temperature of uncoated and Cr₃C₂-NiCr-coated superalloys in a molten salt environment (Na₂SO₄-60% V₂O₅) for 100 cycles, the thermogravimetry technique is applied. By employing XRD, SEM, and FE-SEM/EDAX to introduce their microstructural and compositional characteristics, the erosion products of the detonation gun-sprayed Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings on superalloys are examined in order to clarify the erosion mechanisms. In the provided molten salt environment at 900 °C, it is demonstrated that Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings on Ni- and Fe-based superalloy substrates are particularly efficient in reducing the erosion rate. In particular, compared to Superni 75 and Superni 718, the coating applied to Superfer 800 H provided superior erosion resistance. Ash fouling in coal-fired utility boilers Monitoring and optimization of on-load cleaning under cyclic thermal loading conditions at 900°C, the behavior of Cr₂O₃ composite coatings solidified with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) has been studied in the boiler environment of a thermal power plant. The coatings were applied using the high-velocity oxy-fuel technique, with the CNT concentration ranging from 1 to 8 wt%. Weight change analysis was used to compare the impacts of varying CNT content (from 1 to 8 wt%) on the behavior of hot corrosion, and the corrosion products were examined using X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, energy dispersive, and cross-sectional analysis methods [14].

Hidalgo studied the erosion resistance of Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings applied to Superni 75, Superni 718, and Superfer 800 H superalloys using a detonation cannon (D-gun). These superalloy substrates'

deposited coatings have a virtually homogeneous, adherent, and dense microstructure with a porosity of less than 0.8%. In order to evaluate the high temperature of uncoated and Cr₃C₂-NiCr-coated superalloys in a molten salt environment (Na₂SO₄-60% V₂O₅) for 100 cycles, the thermogravimetry technique is applied. By employing XRD, SEM, and FE-SEM/EDAX to introduce their microstructural and compositional characteristics, the erosion products of the detonation gun-sprayed Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings on superalloys are examined in order to clarify the erosion mechanisms. In the provided molten salt environment at 900 °C, it is demonstrated that Cr₃C₂-NiCr coatings on Ni- and Fe-based superalloy substrates are particularly efficient in reducing the erosion rate. In particular, compared to Superni 75 and Superni 718, the coating applied to Superfer 800 H provided superior erosion resistance [15].

Praveen reported the It has been difficult to control high-temperature corrosion issues in biomass-fired boilers, in part because of the large concentrations of chemically active chemicals, in particular alkali chlorides. Low-alloy substrate materials can be protected in areas sensitive to high-temperature corrosion by thermally sprayed coatings with a high chromium concentration. For two years, the Fe-27Cr-11Ni-4Mo and Fe-19Cr-9W-7Nb-4Mo thermally sprayed (HVOF-coated tubes were situated in the boiler's hot economizer, where the maximum material temperature was thought to be around 200 °C. high velocity) coatings were subjected to biomass boiler conditions. Mostly wood-based fuels combined with small amounts of clay were used in the liquid-bed boiler for district heating. The coated tubes were placed in the boiler's hot economizer, where the maximum material temperature was thought to be around 200 °C. Following exposure, SEM-EDX was used to investigate the coatings and the carbon steel St35.8 substrate material [16].

Ramesh reported that in this publication, outcomes from research on laser-treated Cr-Ni base coatings in steam boilers with 3-3.5 vol% free oxygen at 773 and 1073 K are presented. By weighing samples, the whole oxidation process has been quantified. SEM was used together with a wavelength mounted on a gray spectrometer (WDS) to analyze the oxidized layers. The outcomes were contrasted with the oxidation results of various Cr-Ni plasma-sprayed coatings and AISI 304 stainless steel that had previously been tested. The laser-treated coating's significantly higher oxidation resistance compared to untreated AISI 304 and the identical plasma-sprayed coating are attributed to its lack of pores and the development of a thin, oxidized protective film [17].

Varela studied The detonation results showed an unwanted scatter when they were spurted out of the barrel's nozzle at high velocity and pressure during the detonation gun (D-gun) spraying procedure. A separating mechanism was included in the detonation gun spraying system to address this issue. The D-gun spraying technology was used to create the WC-Co coatings either with or without the use of a separating mechanism. Air plasma spray is where the carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composite is. In this publication, outcomes from research on laser-treated Cr-Ni base coatings in steam boilers with 3-3.5 vol% free oxygen at 773 and 1073 K are presented. By weighing samples, the whole oxidation process has been quantified. SEM was used together with an energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) and a wavelength mounted on a gray spectrometer (WDS) to analyze the oxidized layers. increasing the torch scan speed and decreasing the spraying distance [18].

Conshohocken reported that under isothermal circumstances at a temperature of 900°C, the oxidation behavior of T-91 steel and T-22 steel in salts of 75 weight percent Na₂SO₄ and 25 weight percent NaCl has been investigated in a cyclic way. At 900°C, oxidation kinetics for T-91 steel and T-22 steel in salt were developed. Using the thermogravimetric method for 50 cycles under cyclic circumstances. Each cycle took two hours to complete: one hour of heating at 900°C and 20 minutes of cooling in the air. Both samples almost followed the oxidation-parabolic rate rule. The oxide scales were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy/energy dispersive X-ray (SEM/EDAX) methods. During salt oxidation, T-91 steel was shown to be more erosion-resistant than T-22 steel [19].

Kunioshi studied the high-temperature erosion wear of flame and plasma-sprayed nickel-chromium coatings under simulated coal-fired boiler atmospheres. A SEM image of the powder feedstock, alongside a BSE SEM image of the powder cross sections, shows that the particles of WC-Co are roughly spherical in shape, with an exterior covered in grains of WC. The mean carbide grain size was measured at approximately 3. Cross-sectional BSE images show the WC phase embedded in the Co binder phase with a darker contrast, along with porosity visible inside the particles, typical of agglomerated and sintered powders. The NiCrFeSiB particles are the larger spherical gray particles, seen to be larger in size than the WC-Co particles. Cross-sectional SEM images indicated these particles are non-porous, with two distinct phases being visible. Measurements from EDX point scans of these two phases are shown. The spots with the darker contrast within the Ni phase particles were found to be Cr-rich, with Ni content falling from around 70.9 wt% in the surrounding areas to 29.5 wt% in the Cr-rich regions [20].

4. Conclusion

The parameters affecting erosion include material properties, environmental factors, and process parameters. The erosion modes were reviewed according to the media causing erosion, i.e., liquid impingement erosion, solid particle erosion, and slurry erosion.

Comparison of the results of different erosion tests is often unreliable due to the wear being strongly influenced by the variation of key parameters responsible for it. Even minor variations, e.g., particle velocity and flow direction, may have a strong influence on erosion test results. The use of reference materials that are tested at the same time or under identical conditions as the test samples is advisable for enabling comparison of results.

The most common methods to measure wear involve direct determination of the amount of removed material as mass loss or volume loss.

5. References

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